

Appendix 3. Rule selection and execution algorithm (ECA-based runtime adaptation)

Input:

e: current event (e.g., InitialLoad, ExplicitUserAdaptation, UserBehavior, NavigationContextChange, ...)

RuleRepo: rule repository

Profiles: available profiles {UPu, UCPUT, WIPw, UBPuwt}

DOM: current document (DOM + computed styles)

ActionsLibrary: catalog of adaptation primitives

GuardrailsRepo: guardrail constraints loaded from an external file, indexed by WIA attribute

ExplicitRequest: boolean (true if the adaptation was explicitly requested by the user or an assistive tool)

Req: optional request payload (source, targetAttr in WIA/WIC, and parameters, if ExplicitRequest = true)

Output:

Trace: execution traces (per-invocation applied/skipped/failed)

UpdatedProfiles: updated profiles (mainly WIPw)

Procedure SelectAndAdapt(e, RuleRepo, Profiles, DOM, ActionsLibrary, GuardrailsRepo, ExplicitRequest, Req):

1. if e == InitialLoad then
2. ChangedAttributes <- empty set
3. end if

4. // 1) Select candidate rules (by event and status)
5. Candidates <- { r in RuleRepo | r.Status == active and r.Event == e }

6. // Optional: if this is an explicit request targeting an attribute, restrict by coverage
7. if ExplicitRequest == true and Req != null then
8. Candidates <- { r in Candidates | Req.targetAttr in r.ModifiedAttributes }
9. end if

10. // 2) Filter by condition (applicable rules)
11. Applicable <- empty list
12. for each r in Candidates do
13. if Evaluate(r.Conditions, Profiles) == true then
14. Append(Applicable, r)
15. end if
16. end for

17. // 3) Sort by priority with deterministic tie-breaking
18. Applicable <- Sort(Applicable, key = (r.Priority, r.IdRule))

19. // 4) Conservative execution with guardrails (partial execution)
20. AppliedTarget <- false
21. for each r in Applicable do
22. // 4.1 User confirmation (if required by this rule)
23. if r.AutoExecutable == false then
24. if UserConfirm(r) == false then
25. Trace <- Trace U { (e, r.IdRule, "SKIP_RULE", "UserRejected") }
26. continue
27. end if
28. end if

29. // 4.2 Execute the action sequence invocation by invocation
30. for each inv in r.Action do
31. (name, args) <- inv
32. attr <- field(name, ActionsLibrary)

33. // Overwrite prevention per target attribute
34. if attr in ChangedAttributes then

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35.     Trace <- Trace U { (e, r.IdRule, name, "SKIP_INV", "AttributeAlreadyChanged") }
36.     continue
37. end if

38. // Accessibility guardrails (before executing this invocation)
39. if GuardrailsFail(attr, inv, Profiles, DOM, GuardrailsRepo) then
40.     Trace <- Trace U { (e, r.IdRule, name, "SKIP_INV", "GuardrailViolation") }
41.     continue
42. end if

43. // Execute primitive invocation
44. old <- GetProfileValue(WIPw, attr)
45. ok <- ExecutePrimitive(inv, DOM, ActionsLibrary)
46. if ok == false then
47.     Trace <- Trace U { (e, r.IdRule, name, "FAIL_INV", "ExecutionError") }
48.     continue
49. end if

50. // Post-actions: incremental profile update and traceability
51. UpdateObservedValue(WIPw, attr, DOM)
52. UpdateDerivedAttributes(WIPw, attr, DOM) // optional dependency refresh
53. new <- GetProfileValue(WIPw, attr)
54. ChangedAttributes <- ChangedAttributes U { attr }
55. Trace <- Trace U { (e, r.IdRule, name, "APPLY_INV", attr, old, new) }

56. if ExplicitRequest == true and Req != null and attr == Req.targetAttr then
57.     AppliedTarget <- true
58. end if
59. end for
60. end for

61. // 5) Default fallback (only for explicit requests not satisfied by any executed invocation)
62. if ExplicitRequest == true and Req != null and AppliedTarget == false then
63.     invfb <- BuildFallbackInvocation(Req, ActionsLibrary) // returns an invocation or null
64.     if invfb == null then
65.         Trace <- Trace U { (e, "FALLBACK", "SKIP", "NoDefaultMapping") }
66.     else
67.         (fname, fargs) <- invfb
68.         fattr <- field(fname, ActionsLibrary)
69.         if fattr in ChangedAttributes then
70.             Trace <- Trace U { (e, "FALLBACK", fname, "SKIP_INV", "AttributeAlreadyChanged") }
71.         else if GuardrailsFail(fattr, invfb, Profiles, DOM, GuardrailsRepo) then
72.             Trace <- Trace U { (e, "FALLBACK", fname, "SKIP_INV", "GuardrailViolation") }
73.         else
74.             old <- GetProfileValue(WIPw, fattr)
75.             ok <- ExecutePrimitive(invfb, DOM, ActionsLibrary)
76.             if ok == false then
77.                 Trace <- Trace U { (e, "FALLBACK", fname, "FAIL_INV", "ExecutionError") }
78.             else
79.                 UpdateObservedValue(WIPw, fattr, DOM)
80.                 UpdateDerivedAttributes(WIPw, fattr, DOM) // optional dependency refresh
81.                 new <- GetProfileValue(WIPw, fattr)
82.                 ChangedAttributes <- ChangedAttributes U { fattr }
83.                 Trace <- Trace U { (e, "FALLBACK", fname, "APPLY_INV", fattr, old, new) }
84.             end if
85.         end if
86.     end if
87. end if

88. return (Trace, Profiles)

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